
Creation of Ready to Wear Deluxe with Manipulating Fabric Slashing Inspired by the Golden Sunrise of Bromo

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Abstract

The creation of this work is based on a type of practice-led research approach carried out through a fashion design practice studio with a focus on "Penciptaan Raedy to Wear Deluxe dengan Manipulating Fabric Slashing Terinspirasi dari Golden Sunrise of Bromo". This creative practice study aims to convey the creativity of fashion design which can increase the repertoire of forms and types of clothing that are different from previously existing clothing. This work was inspired by the golden sunrise of Bromo which has its own uniqueness in terms of beautiful and unique visuals and is still very minimally applied or realized as an inspiration for the concept of work by a previous designer. To achieve this goal, the method used in making this work goes through four stages, namely: pre-design, design, embodiment, and presentation by applying the technique of manipulating fabric slashing to the clothing so that it can add creative and aesthetic value to the clothing. The results of this creation process were 2 ready to wear deluxe works which were presented in the form of a fashion show at the 34th Annual UNESA Fashion Show "BHUMIBRAMA" using an outdoor on the floor fashion show presentation technique.

Keywords: ready to wear deluxe, manipulating fabric slashing, golden sunrise of Bromo

Abstrak

Penciptaan karya ini didasarkan pada jenis pendekatan practice-led research yang dilakukan melalui studio praktik perancangan busana dengan fokus "penciptaan ready to wear deluxe dengan manipulating fabric slashing terinspirasi dari golden sunrise of Bromo". Studi praktik penciptaan ini bertujuan menyampaikan kreativitas perancangan busana yang dapat menambah perbendaharaan bentuk dan jenis busana yang berbeda dari busana yang ada sebelumnya. Pengayaan ini terinspirasi dari golden sunrise of Bromo yang memiliki keunikan

tersendiri dari segi visual yang indah, dan unik serta masih sangat minim diaplikasikan atau diwujudkan sebagai inspirasi konsep karya oleh seorang desainer sebelumnya. Untuk mencapai tujuan tersebut, maka metode yang digunakan dalam pembuatan karya ini melalui empat tahap, yaitu: pra-perancangan, perancangan, perwujudan, dan penyajian dengan mengaplikasikan teknik manipulating fabric slashing pada bagian busana sehingga dapat menambah nilai kreativitas dan estetika busana. Hasil proses penciptaan ini berupa 2 karya ready to wear deluxe yang disajikan dalam bentuk pagelaran busana atau fashion show di 34th Annual Fashion Show UNESA "BHUMIBRAMA" dengan teknik penyajian fashion show on the floor secara outdoor.

Kata kunci: *ready to wear deluxe, manipulating fabric slashing, golden sunrise of Bromo*

Introduction

Indonesia is a country that passes through the world's mountain routes, so many active volcanoes are found. Data from the Smithsonian Institution Global Volcanism Program, from 1960 to 2023, there were 55 active volcanoes in Indonesia. One of these active volcanoes is Mount Bromo. This mountain is located in four regions, namely, Probolinggo, Pasuruan, Lumajang, and Malang. Tourdejava (2015) stated that even though it has the status of an active volcano, Mount Bromo is still able to attract the attention of domestic and foreign tourists as the most popular natural tourist destination in East Java, Indonesia. Zalliandi et al. (2023) stated that Mount Bromo is famous for its very beautiful natural views, one of the icons is the sunrise. The interesting thing when visiting Mount Bromo is the "Golden sunrise of Bromo".

Golden sunrise of Bromo is the beauty of the sunrise on Mount Bromo. The morning panorama of Mount Bromo is very popular with domestic and foreign tourists. Singgalen, Y. A (2023) and Widodo et al. (2019) argue that Mount Bromo sunrise is the second most popular word in tourist reviews on Mount Bromo after the word Mount Bromo with the number 1124. It can be concluded that Mount Bromo sunrise is very popular with domestic and foreign tourists.

Wisata Gunung Bromo (2021), states that the unique sunrise of Mount Bromo can be seen from 7 places, namely: 1) climb 1 with a height of 2,770 meters above sea level, 2) seruni point, 3) kingkong / kedaluh hill, 4) love hill, 5) hill mentigen, 6) post dingklik, and 7) peak songolikur Lumajang. These seven places offer different views. Khairanti & Akhrani (2023) stated that Mount Bromo is the only active volcano surrounded by a very large sand caldera. Usually calderas in active volcanic areas are calderas that have the potential for water in them. Tourists must climb to Pananjakan Peak which is the best location to see the sunrise. The tiredness you get when climbing will be paid off with an extraordinary view of the sunrise.

The beauty of the sunrise on Mount Bromo which can be seen from Pananjakan 1 at a height of 2,770 meters above sea level is the most popular place for tourists to see the sunrise on Mount Bromo. The beauty of the rays of the rising sun moving slowly, showing the gradations of sky color from orange to yellow in the blue sky, as well as the dashing and exotic background of Mount Batok, Mount Bromo and the peak of Semuru became a source of

inspiration for the creation of ready to wear deluxe clothing. The choice of colors in this ready to wear deluxe will represent a visualization of the atmosphere of the sunrise and the majesty of Mount Bromo, namely yellow, terracotta and beige. The outer shape of Mount Bromo will be presented as a fashion silhouette. The texture of Mount Bromo will be presented in the choice of materials used.

Atkinson (2012), Ready to wear deluxe is a fashion product whose manufacture uses high quality materials and embellishments, and requires good worker skills. Sari et al. (2023), ready to wear deluxe clothing is ready to wear clothing using patterns that are not too complicated, but are more complex than ready to wear, and the process takes a little longer and requires the help of other people to wear. Diwanti et al. (2023) said that Ready to wear deluxe is ready-to-wear clothing designed with a limited quantity of clothing and good quality. Ready to wear deluxe clothing is also called limited edition clothing design.

Based on the definitions above, it can be concluded that ready to wear deluxe is ready to wear clothing that uses high quality materials and embellishments and the level of workmanship takes slightly longer than ready to wear clothing. Ready to wear deluxe was chosen because researchers wanted to design clothing that was easy to wear, had an exclusive, classy impression, and was able to accommodate the creator's creative ideas. The manipulating fabric slashing accent is applied to several parts of the clothing that will be designed.

McKenna Linn quoted in Sevi & Russanti (2019), the slashing technique is several layers of fabric that are sewn together in parallel and regularly, then one or more layers are cut leaving the bottom layer of fabric intact. Then, feathery effects like pile velvet or faux chenille are created. Yusuf (2018), Fabric slashing is a technique for manipulating fabric, by stacking several fabrics and then cutting one or several layers from the pile of fabric. Harianti et al. (2022) states that fabric slashing is a technique for manipulating fabric using several piles of fabric which are cut according to the shape or pattern of the design by exposing the top layer of the pile so that the surface of the fabric underneath can be seen as a result of the creation being displayed. Widiastuti (2022) defines fabric slashing as a technique for beautifying clothing by bringing out the texture and color of the lowest or most basic layer of fabric. Small (2017) states that manipulating fabric slashing has various techniques including: (1) layering technique, (2) adding a piece of layer, (3) inserting a stack, (4) grids.

Based on the definitions above, it can be concluded that slashing is a technique of manipulating fabric or engineering materials by placing several piles of material which are then cut on the top layer of fabric so that the color appears on the bottom or base surface of the fabric in order to beautify the visualization of the work being created. produced.

M. J. Pingki, S. Hasine, And Md. I. Rahman (2019) said that the slashing technique is widely used by textile artists to provide good texture and interesting effects to their work. Ermalena, et al (2021) concluded that the creation of innovative works by applying the kawung motif using the slashing technique on a 2 face blazer by applying a zero waste pattern could be realized well. Product innovation creates new and different things from before. Apart from that, the zero waste pattern applied can minimize the remaining waste from the quilts and blazers which are made to have 2 functions. Research by N. Made, A. Kartika, n.d. (2023) entitled

"Ready to wear deluxe Fashion Style Inspired by Images of Depression Sufferers (Case Study: Application of Motifs to Clothing)". The research results show that clothing design can be implemented by depression sufferers through clothing motifs or patterns and has aesthetic value in its design.

Based on the three studies above, it inspired researchers to apply manipulating fabric slashing because it is believed to provide a texture that interprets Mount Bromo and provides novelty in the clothing that will be designed.

In this final assignment, the researcher designed two ready to wear deluxes, namely 1 male design inspired by the majesty of Mount Bromo at sunrise and 1 female design inspired by the sunrise movement of Mount Bromo. The target market in this design is teenagers to adults with an age range of 18-27 years and who have a casual or streetwear style. The aim of the researcher was to choose the concept of golden sunrise of Bromo because the researcher wanted to show that the beauty of Mount Bromo's sunrise can be expressed in ready to wear deluxe clothing designs by manipulating fabric slashing which is expected to add to the repertoire of different shapes and types of clothing from before. Adding references for creating creative and innovative clothing by using manipulating fabric slashing.

Research Method

Supendi, E., & Isnanta, S. D. (2020), the systematic realization of a work is the definition of a research method. Stages of creating a work of art which outlines the design of the process of creating a work of art in accordance with the stages of creation from getting the inspiration (idea), designing, to realizing the work of art.

The research method used in this research is a work creation procedure with a Practice-Ied-Research approach or practical research, this research is research that leads to a new understanding of practice and it is put into practice with a focus on "Creating Ready to Wear Deluxe With Inspired Manipulating Fabric Slashing from Golden Sunrise of Bromo". Based on the description above, the Practice-Ied-Research research stages can be written as follows :

Pre-design is also called the exploration stage, activities include exploring sources of

inspiration, data collection and references. At this stage the researcher looks for inspiration and information as a guide in determining the design concept to be created. The design stage is the stage of creating a design plan for the product to be made. In this creation, the researcher created a moodboard and fashion design that refers to the moodboard and design concept. The realization stage is the stage of turning a product that has been designed into a real work. In this creation, the realization of the work goes through two stages, namely the realization in the form of a prototype and the realization of the work using actual materials. Presentation of the work is the final stage in the creation of the work. At this stage, the finished work can be published to the general public as a form of work promotion. This can take the form of exhibitions or certain events such as fashion shows. Apart from being published, the work that has been created can also be evaluated to ensure that the work that has been created is in accordance with the planned concept or theme.

Result and Discussion

The creation of this work used the Practice-Ied-Research creation method through 4 stages. In connection with the discussion related to the output of the prototype/model/prototype resulting from Parctice-led Research, the realization process is carried out through four stages, such as: exploration, work design, work realization, and work dissemination. The four stages can be explained as follows:

A. Exploration / Pre-design

Exploration is the same stage as pre-design which contains analysis of problems in the field and solutions obtained. The exploration stage can be described as follows:

1. Inspiration Source Exploration Stage

At the exploration source of inspiration stage, the researcher conducts research, collects information and observes the sources of inspiration that will be selected and also determines the target market. The source of inspiration for this creation was the Golden Sunrise of Bromo, which means the beauty of the sunrise with the backdrop of Mount Batok, Mount Bromo and Puncak Semeru. From the inspiration source image, the researcher observed the shape, texture, color, identity and target market.

The target market for this creation is men and women with an age range of 18-27 years,

who have a streetwear / casual style in their daily lives, and have middle to upper income.

2. Design Concept Exploration Stage

Exploration of design concepts is the researcher's stage in creating design concepts that serve as guidelines for designing clothing. At this stage, the researcher will describe in detail the design concept created in the form of a moodboard. The following is a moodboard for creating ready to wear deluxe by manipulating fabric slashing inspired by the golden sunrise of Bromo.

The moodboard above explains several points including:

- The brand signature in this creation is street casual
- The male design concept will focus on the majesty of Mount Bromo and Mount Batok, so the designs created are in the form of jackets and trousers.
- The female design concept will represent the beauty and elegance of the sunrise, so the female design concept is in the form of a dress, top, outer and skirt
- The choice of colors in Male's design is visualized in the appearance of Mount Bromo, namely beige, milo and terracotta. Meanwhile, the choice of colors for the female

design visualizes the beauty, elegance and joy of the sunrise in the form of yellow, terracotta, beige and milo.

- e. The choice of materials for men's and women's designs is different, this difference is due to factors such as the focus of the source of inspiration, design and occasion of clothing use. For the male design, baby canvas is used, while the female design uses Ayumi Japan.
- f. The identity of the source of this inspiration is wrinkle and slashing. Wrinkle represents the texture of Mount Bromo and is striped and wrinkled, while slashing represents the texture of Mount Batok.

3. Exploration Stage Manipulating Fabric

After creating a design concept, the next step is to determine the fabric manipulation that will be applied in this creation. This creation uses manipulating fabric slashing which will give a deluxe impression to the clothing design. The slashing was chosen based on the texture of the inspirational image of Mount Batok whose surface is covered with several plants and grass so that it has the impression of an unfinished hairy texture.

B. Work Design

1. Alternative Design

Alternative designs are all designs that are created and developed based on the source of ideas used. The number of alternative designs that will be created in this research is 5 ready-to-wear men's designs and 5 ready-to-wear deluxe women's designs.

2. Selected design

The selected design is the best design chosen based on the results of consultation and evaluation from two experts in the design and fashion fields. The number of selected

designs that were realized was 2 designs, namely 1 men's ready-to-wear deluxe design and 1 women's ready-to-wear deluxe design. Based on the results of consultations with the supervisor of the creative work course, the selected men's deluxe ready-to-wear design consisted of 2 works, namely male and female. The following is a description of the selected designs:

a. Ready to wear deluxe male design

The first part is a body covering which is made into a turtleneck sweater. The outer part of the sweater is made into a jacket with a wide and high collar development. Meanwhile, the second part is covering the lower body in the form of trousers with a length below the knee. Manipulating fabric slashing is applied to the collar which is the accent/center of interest of the jacket design. Apart from that, manipulating fabric slashing is also a textured motif for the jacket.

b. Ready to wear deluxe female design

The selected ready to wear deluxe female design consists of 2 parts, namely the sleeveless dress part with the dress length below the knee and the outer part in the form of an outer croptop which applies manipulating fabric slashing on the front.

3. Working Drawings

Working drawings or often known as technical drawings are techniques for drawing ideas in detail, before they become prototypes and are produced. Technical drawing is needed to minimize errors or missing details that will be made and has a function as a translator. Working drawings in the creation of ready to wear deluxe help in reading the details of the clothing design, all details of the clothing, including flat drawings, clothing

described as follows:

1. Work Creation Process 1

In the process of making work 1 there are several stages, the following are the stages in the process of making work 1:

a. Ready to wear deluxe men's clothing production process

The ready to wear deluxe men's clothing production process starts from measuring the model's body during the model audition, making pattern breaks according to the design, cutting the material, and the process of sewing the clothing using techniques that are in accordance with the techniques for sewing lined jackets and sewing techniques for men's trousers.

b. Manufacturing stage manipulating fabric slashing

In work 1, the application of manipulating fabric slashing is located on the collar of the jacket. The process of making slashing is done by stacking 3 layers of long fabric with a width of 3 cm and the length is adjusted to the shape of the collar. Then stitched and the final stage is finished unfinished. Following are the results of manipulating fabric slashing on the jacket collar.

c. Fitting Stage

In fashion design, the fitting stage is an important stage to ensure that the clothes not only look good aesthetically but are also comfortable when worn. In the process of realizing this work, two fittings were carried out, fitting 1 using a prototype and fitting 2 using actual materials.

2. Process of Making Work 2

In the process of making work 2 there are several stages, the following are the stages in the process of making work 2:

a. Women's ready-to-wear deluxe fashion production process

The production process for ready-to-wear deluxe women's clothing starts from measuring the model's body during the model audition, making broken patterns according to the design using a construction pattern with standard size M, cutting the material, and the process of sewing the clothes using techniques that match the techniques for sewing dresses using closed lining and technique for sewing an outer crop top with a lining finish.

b. Manufacturing stage manipulating fabric slashing

In work 2, the application of manipulating fabric slashing is located on the outer part. The process of making slashing is done by stacking 3 layers of long cloth with a width of 3 cm and the length is adjusted to the outer shape. Then stitched and the final stage is finished unfinished. Following are the results of manipulating fabric slashing on the jacket collar.

c. Fitting Stage

In fashion design, the fitting stage is an important stage to ensure that the clothes not only look good aesthetically but are also comfortable when worn. In the process of realizing this work, two fittings were carried out, fitting 1 using a prototype and fitting 2 using actual materials.

D. Review of Works

1. Work Description (1)

In creating this ready to wear deluxe male, baby canvas was used for the jacket and trousers. The next characteristic of ready to wear deluxe is the technique of manipulating fabric to add texture, dimension and unique details to clothing designs. The use of manipulating fabric slashing can give a unique touch to the ready to wear deluxe collection, so that the clothing design is not only comfortable to wear but also looks aesthetically pleasing. In creating this ready to wear deluxe male, manipulating fabric slashing is used on the high collar.

The choice of slashing as a clothing detail was based on the source of inspiration for the texture of Mount Bromo. The shape of Mount Bromo is applied to the silhouette of the jacket which looks bulging at the bottom of the jacket. The color of the sunrise is presented in the colors of the clothing collection, namely beige on the jacket and knee pant and terracotta on the sweater. The rays of the rising sun are presented in the manipulating fabric slashing pattern found on the high collar of the jacket.

2. Work Description (2)

In the creation of this ready to wear deluxe female, Ayumi Japan materials were used. The next characteristic of ready to wear deluxe is the technique of manipulating fabric to add texture, dimension and unique details to clothing designs. The use of manipulating fabric slashing can give a unique touch to the ready to wear deluxe collection, so that the clothing design is not only comfortable to wear but also stands out from an aesthetic perspective. In creating this ready to wear deluxe female, manipulating fabric slashing is used on the outer part.

The choice of slashing as a clothing detail was based on the source of inspiration for the texture of Mount Bromo. The shape of Mount Bromo is applied to clothing silhouettes, namely in cutting that uses a curved shape like Mount Bromo. The sunrise color is presented in the clothing collection, namely terracotta on the dress and yellow on the outer. The rays of the rising sun are presented in a manipulating fabric slashing pattern on the outer.

E. Dissemination of Works

After the work is realized, the next stage is the dissemination of the work. This form of dissemination of the work of creating ready to wear deluxe by manipulating fabric slashing, inspired by the golden sunrise of Bromo, was published through two activities, namely a grand jury and a fashion show. The following is the form of presentation of the work chosen:

1. Grand Jury is the stage of evaluating works in creative works. This activity takes the form of a closed presentation of the designer's work which is then evaluated and given criticism and suggestions by the jury. There are 3 (three) judges in this activity, namely Elizabeth Njo May Fen, Ulfa Mumtaza and Dra. Indah Chrysanti Angge, M.Sn. Based on the results of the jury's evaluation on May 6 2023, the creation of this work received appreciation for the fabric manipulation applied. For the design concept as a source of ideas, the choice of collection colors, the choice of materials is appropriate, but for design development it still needs to be improved.

2. The fashion show/fashion show is held in two forms of presentation, namely offline in the courtyard of the Unesa rectorate with the title 34TH Annual Fashion Show "BHUMIBRAMA" UNESA and online (live streaming) on YouTube AFS Unesa on 27 May 2023. Fashion event The show was held outdoors and collaborated with theater, where not only models walked on the runway, but there was a theatrical performance that told the source of the idea and built an atmosphere from the source of the idea taken, namely the golden sunrise of Bromo. The form of presenting this fashion show is on the floor, which means it does not require a special stage, the position of the audience and models are at the same level. Based on these activities, the creation of this work received appreciation as the best monumental textile which was read by the jury at the end of the event.

Conclusion

The final task of fashion work in the form of creating a ready to wear deluxe by manipulating fabric slashing inspired by the golden sunrise of Bromo has gone through several stages so that the process of creating this final work can be completed.

The process of realizing the ready to wear deluxe fashion by manipulating fabric slashing inspired by the golden sunrise of Bromo is guided by the method of creating works with a practice led-research approach through four stages, namely the pre-design/exploration stage, design, realization and presentation. From these four stages it can be concluded that the golden sunrise of Bromo can not only be enjoyed visually, but the beauty of the sunrise on Mount Bromo can be used as inspiration for the creation of ready to wear deluxe clothing which can be seen both through aesthetics and visualization. Presented in fashion silhouettes, the color selection of the fashion collection is based on the colors of the golden sunrise of Bromo, namely yellow, terracotta and beige, the texture of Mount Bromo can be used as a source of inspiration for manipulating fabric slashing which will be applied to ready to wear deluxe clothing and will add creative value and aesthetics in clothing.

Apart from creating ready to wear deluxe clothing, the creation of this work reached the stage of presenting the work which was presented in a fashion show at the 34th Annual UNESA Fashion Show entitled "BHUMIBRAMA". The fashion show was held outdoors with the concept of a fashion show on the floor.

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